

Survey on Automated Video Game Testing

Hi. My name is Cristiano Politowski. I'm a Ph.D. student at Concordia University. My thesis is about automated video game testing techniques. Here is my LinkedIn:

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/cristiano-politowski/>

I would like to, kindly ask for 5-10 minutes of your time to help my research by filling this form.

This questionnaire is designed to understand the real need of the industry regarding video game testing. This study investigates the automated video game testing techniques in academic papers as well as the video game industry needs. In special, video game testers.

The results of the survey will be used in an article for the Workshop on Games and Software Engineering (<https://sites.google.com/fbk.eu/gas2022/home>). I will share the pre-print in this link: <https://cpoli.live/publications/> (or, if you opt for it, send it to you directly via email)

All the information you provide will be kept confidential.

In particular, we have no intention of judging you as a person—we are merely interested in learning about the relevance of certain topics to your work.

If you have any questions, please contact me at c_polito@encs.concordia.ca

Thank you very much!

Cristiano Politowski - Ptidej Team - Department of Software Engineering - Concordia University - Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Required

0. Background

1. Your experience developing video games *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Less than 2 years
- Less than 3 years
- Less than 4 years
- More than 4 years

2. Which one best describes your job role? *

Mark only one oval.

- Game Programmer
- Game Designer
- Game Tester
- Manager
- Artist
- Other: _____

3. Regarding employment, have you have been... *

Mark only one oval.

- Part of a team inside a game studio
- Part of a thid-party team that offers game testing services
- Outsourced
- Other: _____

4. Do you usually play games as a hobby? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

5. Do you have experience as a software developer? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

1. About Manual Testing

6. Which type of testing do you usually do? *

Check all that apply.

Manual playtesting of the game

Playtesting using scripts

Playtesting using the game engine tools

Other: _____

7. When you test the game, you usually do... *

Check all that apply.

Balancing the game mechanics

Exploring and checking the game content

Searching for bugs

Other: _____

8. When you test the game, you usually try to spot... *

Check all that apply.

- Crash (the game freezes or exits)
- Stuck (soft-lock, when the player cannot progress)
- Graphical issues (rendering glitches)
- Performance issues (low framerates for example)
- Colision issues

Other: _____

2. Academic Techniques

This section asks you to evaluate academic ideas we got from scientific papers.

2.1 Testing for **BALANCING** the game mechanics

9. [Idea #1] Human-Like Playtesting with Deep Learning (2018) | Game used: Candy Crush *

GOAL: Test the difficulty of a game level. HOW: Use autonomous agents (bots) to simulate human gameplay and the "success rate" with human players. AUTOMATION: The agents' goal is to predict the difficulty of a new game level automatically. RESULTS: the difficulty of new levels could be tested automatically.

(a) Train a CNN agent

(b) Fit a binomial regression model

(c) Predict human success rate for new levels

Mark only one oval per row.

No Not sure Yes

[Desirability]

Is this something you would like to use for game testing?

[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?

[Feasibility] For you, do you believe this idea would bring benefits to game testing?

10. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

11. [Idea #2] Predicting Game Difficulty and Churn Without Players (2020) | Game used: Angry Birds Dream Blast *

GOAL: Predict pass rate (win the game) and churn (abandon the game) in new levels of the game. HOW: Use gameplay data from autonomous agents (bots) and playtesters. AUTOMATION: Train agents (bots) to play the game autonomously. RESULTS: the pass rate and churn of new levels could be tested automatically.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No	Not sure	Yes
<hr/>			
<p>[Desirability] Is this something you would like to use for game testing?</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<hr/>			
<p>[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<hr/>			
<p>[Feasibility] For you, do you believe this idea would bring benefits to game testing?</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<hr/>			

12. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

2.2 EXPLORING the game

13. [Idea #3] Improving Playtesting Coverage via Curiosity Driven Reinforcement Learning Agents (2021) | Game tested: 3D third person demo *

GOAL: Testing coverage in complex 3D environments. HOW: Fully traverse the environments using autonomous agents (bots). AUTOMATION: Automate the collection of some playtest data. RESULTS: The agent can reach areas that should not be inaccessible.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No	Not sure	Yes
[Desirability] Is this something you would like to use for game testing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Feasibility] For you, do you believe this idea would bring benefits to	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

game
testing?

14. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

15. [Idea #4] Playtesting: What is Beyond Personas (2020) | Game tested: 2D
Adventure and Doom clone *

GOAL: Discover different paths at the level. HOW: Use autonomous agents (bots) with different personas (killer, explorer, etc). AUTOMATION: Automate the exploration of the game. RESULT: The agent can reach the goal of the game in different ways.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No	Not sure	Yes
[Desirability] Is this something you would like to use for game testing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Feasibility] For you, do you believe this idea would bring benefits to game testing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

17. [Idea #5] Wuji: Automatic Online Combat Game Testing Using Evolutionary Deep Reinforcement Learning (2019) | Game tested: 2D maze and undisclosed MMOG *

GOAL: Explore more game states (corner cases). HOW: Use autonomous agents (bots) with different goals. AUTOMATION: Automate the exploration of the game states. RESULT: The agent can reach non-trivial game states.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No	Not sure	Yes
[Desirability] Is this something you would like to use for game	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

testing?

[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?

[Feasibility] For you, do you believe this idea would bring benefits to game testing?

18. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

2.3 Testing to FIND BUGS

19. [Idea #6] Automated Game Testing with ICARUS: Intelligent Completion of Adventure Riddles via Unsupervised Solving (2017) | Game tested: Adventure *

GOAL: Detect bugs. HOW: Use autonomous agents (bots) to complete the game. AUTOMATION: Complete the playthrough like a speedrun. RESULTS: Automatically spot crashes/freezes and blocker (soft lock).

Mark only one oval per row.

	No	Not sure	Yes
[Desirability] Is this something you would like to use for game testing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Feasibility] For you, do you believe	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

this idea
would bring
benefits to
game
testing?

20. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

21. [Idea #7] Enhancing the Monte Carlo Tree Search Algorithm for Video Game Testing (2020) | Game tested: 2D Adventure *

GOAL: Find the bugs already defined. HOW: Use autonomous agents (bots) to play the game level.

AUTOMATION: The agents generate sequences that can be replayed. RESULTS: The agents explore and spot the bugs.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No	Not sure	Yes
[Desirability] Is this something you would like to use for game testing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[Viability] Do you think it can be implemented in your workflow?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Feasibility]

For you, do you believe this idea would bring benefits to game testing?

22. Do you mind explaining your answer? (optional)

3. About the Future of Video Game Testing

These are all OPTIONAL questions. Feel free to ignore them as you please.

23. What is the most important aspect of video game testing?

24. Currently, what is lacking in the video game industry that could help video game testers do their jobs?

25. In 10 years, how do you think video games will be tested?

Thank you very much!

26. Your email for future updates

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